

H₂ Production by NH₃ Decomposition in a Membrane Reactor: A Comparison with Packed Bed and Use for H₂ Recovery from Diluted Ammonia Streams

Domenico Maccarrone¹, Gianfranco Giorgianni^{1*}, Cristina Italiano², Siglinda Perathoner¹, Gabriele Centi¹, Salvatore Abate^{1*}

¹ Department of ChiBioFarAm, University of Messina, ERIC aisbl and INSTM/CASPE, V.le F. Stagno d'Alcontres 31, Messina 98166, Italy

² Advanced Energy Technology Institute of the National Research Council of Italy (CNR-ITAE), Salita Santa Lucia Sopra Contesse 5, ME, Messina, 98126, Italy

* Corresponding authors: S.A. abates@unime.it; G.G.g.giorgianni@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Ammonia decomposition is a key technology for its use as a hydrogen carrier and in the recovery of H₂ from waste streams containing ammonia. The coupling of the catalytic decomposition of ammonia with an H₂ permeoselective membrane improves the process by mitigating thermodynamic constraints and producing a flux of high-purity hydrogen, not requiring further separation/purification. In this study, we compare the behaviour of an eggshell catalyst 1.3 wt. % Ru/Al₂O₃ catalyst in a packed bed reactor (PBR) and a packed bed membrane reactor (PBMR) using an ultrathin Pd membrane (3.4 μm). Tests were made at 11 bar(a) with a weight hourly space velocity of NH₃ in the 0.560 – 1.68 L·g⁻¹·h⁻¹ range and temperatures of 350 – 400°C, e.g. milder conditions than the conventional ammonia cracking catalysts. Under optimised conditions (0.56 L·g⁻¹·h⁻¹, 400 °C, sweep gas flow 0.55 L·min⁻¹), the PBMR shows excellent performance, achieving NH₃ conversion, H₂ productivity and recovery factor of 99%, 47 mmol_{H₂}·g_{Ru}⁻¹·min⁻¹, and 94.9%, respectively. PBMR increases by ~50% the conversion rate compared to PBR. Without a sweep gas, PBMR performances are lower, even still higher than in PBR. Tests using a 10% NH₃/Ar stream show the applicability of the technology for the valorisation of diluted ammonia stream.

Keywords:

H₂ by NH₃ decomposition
NH₃ cracking
NH₃ as H₂ carrier
Membrane reactor
Packed-bed reactor

1. Introduction

Using green H₂ as an energy carrier is potentially pivotal for minimising the dependence on fossil fuels and promoting energy efficiency [1]. However, conventional H₂ storage, transportation, and safety pose severe challenges to its use. Therefore, several physical and chemical storage methods and utilisation cycles, like the power-to-X, are currently being investigated for converting renewable electricity to methane [2], 2-methyl furan [3], and ammonia. Among these, the chemical storage of H₂ in the ammonia molecule, due to its remarkable energy density (larger than 700 bar pressurised or cryogenic hydrogen) and a lower cost of transport than H₂ [4], is considered a highly potential alternative, especially for long-term storage [5]. These features make ammonia a promising H₂ vector capable of unlocking the use of hydrogen while minimising storage and utilisation costs [6 – 11].

Ammonia decomposition (also indicated by the term ammonia cracking or pyrolysis) is an endothermic reaction that is thermodynamically favoured at high temperatures and low pressures [12] in the presence of inert gases and by removing the formed hydrogen. The reaction has been reported mainly in packed-bed reactors (PBR). Several active metals were investigated for the reaction [13]. Non-noble metals like Ni, Fe, and Co were found to be active only above 450 – 500°C; however, Ru, allowing to operate efficiently between 300 – 500°C, is still considered the most effective, despite its cost [14-17]. The catalyst design and engineering are essential for ensuring the competitiveness of the process. Synthesising well-dispersed metal nanoparticles (NPs) with a high surface/volume ratio is an ongoing challenge to minimise Ru use [18-20]. The shape design of the catalysts, in particular the use of eggshell-type, is also important to reduce heat/mass transport limitations.

In addition to catalyst design, reactor engineering is crucial to enable a cost-effective process working in milder conditions, where heat transfer limitations are less severe, catalyst stability is higher and process electrification is possible. It is necessary to recall some aspects related to the kinetics shortly to understand these aspects,

Using Ru catalysts, Ru/Al₂O₃ in particular, the NH₃ decomposition has activation energy within the 95 – 150 kJ·mol⁻¹ range [21-22]. At low temperatures and high hydrogen partial pressures, hydrogen inhibits the reaction kinetics [22-27], while on Ru/AC (active carbon), with Ru particles of 1 – 2 nm in diameter, even using diluted ammonia mixtures, the order of reaction for the NH₃ decomposition is unitary for NH₃ and between -3/2 and -2 for H₂ [13], e.g. H₂ inhibits the decomposition. The doping with La was used to promote hydrogen desorption on Ru catalysts [28]. Moreover, some studies report that N₂ also inhibits the reaction [22], its desorption being indicated as the rate-determining step on Ru [28], although there is still no consensus. The catalyst's formulation also determines the rate-determining step. For bimetallic Ni-Ru/CeO₂, the dehydrogenation of the adsorbed ammonia was indicated as the rate-limiting step [29]. These kinetic results indicate that hydrogen should be removed from the equilibrium [30] to push the NH₃ conversion rate. In addition, they also indicate that operating with diluted streams containing waste NH₃ is more challenging than feeding only pure ammonia, to which most of the literature data focus attention.

An integrated Pd-membrane reactor is the choice to remove H₂ during ammonia decomposition [30]. Despite the potential advantages, only a few researches address the ammonia decomposition in integrated membrane reactors [31-34], demonstrating improved NH₃ conversions and the production of high-purity hydrogen (close to 99.9%). It was also claimed to have reduced production costs by reactor intensification. Most of the studies used pure ammonia [31-33,35-39], with few of them feeding diluted ammonia streams [10,34,40-45]. The earlier studies primarily focused on the production of high-purity H₂. In contrast, the later publications examined the conversion of diluted NH₃ in the gasification streams of integrated gasification combined cycles (IGCC) [10,42 – 45] or in purge streams from ammonia synthesis plants for environmental remediation [41]. Additionally, these studies explored the use of the produced H₂ in solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs) [40]. Further applications could also be on diluted ammonia streams from other industrial off-gases, agriculture, and animal husbandry containing CO₂, O₂, water vapour, and sulphur-containing compounds

[46-49], after the separation of the critical poisoning components, e.g., by using zeolitic [50,51], or carbon molecular sieves membranes [52].

For the proper design of an integrated membrane reactor for ammonia decomposition, several factors must be considered. In addition, durable membranes must be developed [34,35,53-56]. The optimal coupling of the catalyst's kinetics and membrane permeance should also be realised. Increased NH_3 conversions and hydrogen permeation rates can be obtained by decreasing the Pd membrane thickness [41,57] and increasing the driving force for H_2 permeation, e.g., by using a vacuum pump or a sweep gas. In the latter case, sweep-gas co-feeding mode, e.g. countercurrent or co-current modes, is also relevant. This fact was observed feeding both pure [41,57] and diluted NH_3 [34,58]. This result is due to the increased mass transfer rate along the axial side of the membrane, as also confirmed for other reactions [59]. Accordingly, increased conversions and H_2 permeation rates were reported after increasing the sweep/feed ratios, with a larger effect using a co-current flow rather than a countercurrent flow due to the better driving force in the former case [41,57,59].

In addition, the effect of the feeding mixture composition should also be considered. Specifically, nitrogen, due to the formation of NH_x species on the Pd surface [60], and NH_3 [61-63] have an inhibitory effect on hydrogen permeation and, in turn, on the NH_3 decomposition rate. Ammonia decreases H_2 permeability on Pd membranes, with a detrimental effect already observed with 10% NH_3/H_2 [60,64,65].

These literature results outline the complex and interdependent aspects governing ammonia decomposition and, thus, the relevance of a proper comparison between performances of the same optimised ammonia decomposition catalysts in PBR and PBMR reactors. We focused attention on using a diluted ammonia stream for its applicative interest and the reduced heat/mass transfer limitations (compared to pure NH_3), allowing lower reactor temperatures to achieve a full ammonia conversion. This is beneficial for membrane stability [9,10,66].

The catalyst used is a 1% Ru/ Al_2O_3 with an eggshell configuration, while the UF (ultrathin) Pd membrane was deposited on a ceramic support to enable good mechanical properties. The PBMR reactor was tested in the presence and absence of Ar as sweep gas and compared with the performance of the same catalyst in a packed bed reactor (PBR). The results demonstrate an almost complete conversion of ammonia at 400°C, employing a sweep gas and using lower amounts of Ru and Pd compared to the best results in the literature for comparable systems using pure NH_3 . The results thus indicate the promising possibility of using this technology for H_2 recovery from waste ammonia streams.

2. Methodologies

2.1 Preparation of the catalyst

The Ru-based catalyst was synthesised by temperature-controlled ion exchange method [67] using 1mm $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ spheres (SASOL, SA = 160 m^2g^{-1}) as the support and $\text{RuCl}_3 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as a precursor. The details of the preparation are reported in SI.

2.2 Preparation of the Pd Membrane

A Pd membrane was prepared on the inner mesoporous side of an asymmetric $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ membrane as support (INOPOR) by Electroless plating (EPD) [54,55]. The details are reported in SI.

2.3 Characterisation

The samples were characterised by chemical composition, powder-ray diffraction, Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) surface area, CO pulse chemisorption and temperature programmed reduction (H_2 -TPR), high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HR-TEM), scanning electron microscope (SEM) equipped with an EDX (energy dispersive X-ray analysis) probe, measures of H_2 -permeability of the

Pd membrane. The details of the characterisation methods were reported in SI.

2.4 Testing systems and reactors

The NH_3 decomposition performances were evaluated using a 10% NH_3/Ar mixture feed at a pressure of 11 bar(a) in a) a packed bed reactor (PBR) and b) in a packed bed membrane reactor (PBMR). Further details are given in SI. A PID Microactivity Effi (FR-200, Micromeritics), equipped with two parallel Hastelloy X reactors, tested the performance in the PBR configuration. Experiments in the PBMR were run in the unit described in SI (see also Fig. S1). Tests with and without an Ar sweep gas were made. Details on the analytical aspects are also reported in SI, which also reports the details of the equations and definitions used in this work.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Catalyst Characterisation

XRF chemical analysis of the catalyst indicates an average Ru loading of 1.3 wt.%, with eggshell distribution suggested by EDX analysis in different spot areas..

The XRD spectra of the support and the fresh calcined and used (reduced) catalyst are shown in Figure 1. The support presents the typical Al_2O_3 reflections (PDF 01 - 1303; PDF 46 - 1131) at 46 and 67°, attributed to the (111) and (211) planes, respectively, and the presence of an amorphous phase between 30° and 40°. The calcined catalyst, besides the support reflections, also presents the typical reflections of the tetragonal RuO_2 phase (PDF 40 - 1290) at 27°, 35° and 55° attributed to the (110), (101) and (211) planes. The used catalyst, besides the Al_2O_3 phase, shows only the presence of the metallic hexagonal Ru phase (PDF 01 - 1253), highlighted by the presence of the peaks at 38 (100), 42 (002) at 44° (101), 78°(103) and 85°(201) [69], with the latter two reflections overlapped with the alumina phase. The crystallite size of RuO_x and metallic Ru in the calcined and the used catalysts, as calculated by the Scherrer equation, is 26 and 28 nm, respectively.

Figure 1. XRD of the support, calcined and reduced (used) Ru/ Al_2O_3 catalyst (powered samples increment = 0.02°; 2 θ range = 10-90); (Δ) metallic Ru - (PDF 01 - 1253); (\blacksquare) RuO_2 - (PDF 40 - 1290); (\star) Al_2O_3 (PDF 01 - 1303; PDF 46 - 1131).

Notably, after reduction, no appreciable oxidised phases of Ru were observed, indicating the almost complete reduction of the catalyst.

The BET surface areas and pore volumes of both calcined and reduced catalysts show minimal differences from the parent support, which are attributed to the low Ru loading, as detailed in (Table 1).

Table 1. Porosimetry analysis.

Sample	S _{BET} (m ² ·g ⁻¹) ¹	Pore Volume (cm ³ ·g ⁻¹) ²
γ-Al ₂ O ₃	160	0.45
Ru/ γ-Al ₂ O ₃ - Calcined	155.6	0.44
Ru/ γ-Al ₂ O ₃ – Reduced	171.3	0.49

¹ 0.05 – 0.25 P/P^o² 0.95 P/P^o, adsorption branch

The TPR profile of the fresh calcined catalyst () shows the presence of two reduction peaks at 153 (P1) and 193 °C (P2), respectively. The CO pulse chemisorption reveals a metallic surface area of 0.0530 m²·g_{cat}⁻¹.

The presence of the peak P1 and P2 in the TPR profile of the calcined agrees with the previous literature [70,71] and indicates the presence of a two-step reduction mechanism for Ru, with P1 to the reduction of RuCl₃ and P2 attributed to the reduction of RuO₂ [71]. However, Ru can be considered fully reduced within the tested conditions after the applied catalyst reduction treatment, which agrees with XRD results.

Figure 2. TPR profile of the calcined catalyst (50 mg of catalyst diluted with SiC reduced in 50 NmL·min⁻¹ of 5% H₂/Ar with a temperature ramp of 10°C min⁻¹).

HR-TEM micrographs of as-prepared (a, b) and reduced catalysts (c-f) are shown in Figure 3. Both samples exhibited agglomerates of almost spherical nanoparticles forming a mesoporous network. TEM image of the as-prepared catalyst displays lattice fringes spacing of 0,318 and 0.256 nm (Figure 3b), indexed to the mainly exposed (110) and (101) crystal planes of RuO₂, respectively (JCPDS card no. 40-1290). The spacing of the lattice fringes in the reduced catalyst (Figure 4Figuref) is 0.234, corresponding to (100) planes of metallic Ru (JCPDS card no. 6-663). High-dispersed Ru nanoparticles were revealed with an average size of 5.5 nm in a wide distribution of 1-13 nm (Figure 3c).

The absence of oxidised phases after reduction treatment is consistent with the previously discussed data.

The SEM cross-section micrographs of the as-prepared Pd membrane (Figure 4a-b) show the palladium distribution over the ceramic support and the variation of the grain size distribution of the asymmetric Al₂O₃ support. The measured Pd membrane thickness is between 2.43 and 6.17 (Figure 4a).

The membrane surface shows macrodomains with dimensions of a few microns, which are formed by an assembly of smoothed nanoparticles. Upon catalytic testing, the presence of Ru particles, evidenced as white spots in Figure 4c and confirmed by EDX microanalysis, was attributed to *catalyst dusting*.

Figure 3. HR-TEM micrographs of calcined (a,b) and reduced (c-f) Ru/Al₂O₃ catalyst. The spacing of the lattice fringes in (b) are 0.318 and 0.256, corresponding to (110) and (101) planes of RuO₂ particles (JCPDS 40-1290). The spacing of the lattice fringes in (f) is 0.234, corresponding to (100) planes of Ru particles (JCPDS 6-663). The yellow arrows were used to point out representative particles selected to estimate the particle size.

Figure 4. SEM micrograph of fresh (a-b) in cross-sectional view and planar view of the used (c) Pd membrane, after testing, evidencing the catalyst dusting phenomenon (15 kV).

3.2 Pd Membrane Characterization and H₂ permeability

The hydrogen permeation flux (J_{H_2}) as a function of differential pressure is reported in Figure 5a. By nonlinear regression of the experimental data, both n value and permeance Q can be determined. They are reported in Table 2. A deviation from Sievert's law is evidenced by the n value of 0.83 at all the tested temperatures, with negligible deviations at 375°C. The H₂ permeance values obtained for $n=0.83$, which gave the best fit for the experimental results, were utilised to calculate the apparent activation energy at the set point temperatures by fitting the Arrhenius law (Table 2, Figure 5b), explaining 80% of the experimental variance, with an estimated activation energy (E_a) of 39.4 kJ·mol⁻¹.

The measured Pd membrane thickness, by SEM image, agrees with the calculated thickness based on the deposited Pd (3.44 μm, see

eq. S3) and confirms the preparation of a UF Pd Membrane. The latter agrees with the estimated n value ($n = 0.83$) and activation energy ($39.4 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$). For Pd membranes, n can change between 0.5 and 1. In the first case (Sievert's law), H_2 transport is limited by its bulk diffusion within Pd grains and is typically observed for membrane thicknesses larger than $10 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ [72]. The second case ($n = 1$) is typically encountered when the controlling transport mechanism is the surface adsorption/desorption of H_2 from Pd [73,74]. Similarly, the estimated activation energy ($39.4 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$) is intermediate between the values typically reported for surface-controlled mechanisms ($54 - 146 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$) and the ones reported by the bulk diffusion-limited transport ($< 30 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$) [73,75]. Therefore, in our case, the rate of hydrogen diffusion through the Pd film depends both on the surface and bulk diffusion [73,74]. The 0.8073 Adj. R^2 observed for the Arrhenius fitted plot agrees with this indication.

Figure 5. H_2 Permeability (a) H_2 Flux; (b) H_2 Permeance Activation Energy (values on Table 3) as a function of the reciprocal temperature (the straight line superimposed on the data points is not the fitting straight-line but the linearised $Q(T)\cdot\delta^{-1} = Q_0\cdot\delta^{-1}\cdot e^{-E_a/RT}$ after non-linear regression; $P_p = 1.013 \text{ bar}$; $P_r = 1.5 - 2.7 \text{ bar}$, $\dot{V}_{F,\text{H}_2} = 1 - 1.3 \text{ NL min}^{-1}$).

Table 2. Sievert's law fitting results.

T (°C)	Fitted Parameters			Adj. R^2
	Permeance ($Q\cdot\delta^{-1}$) ($\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}\cdot\text{Pa}^{-1}$)	n	R^2	
350	$1.003\cdot 10^{-5}$	0.83	0.9989	0.9986
375	$1.474\cdot 10^{-5}$			
400	$2.187\cdot 10^{-5}$			
425	$2.397\cdot 10^{-5}$			

Table 3. Arrhenius law fitting results.

Fitted Parameters			
$Q_0\cdot\delta^{-1}$ ($\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}\cdot\text{Pa}^{-1}$)	E_a ($\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$)	R^2	Adj. R^2
0.02213	39.35	0.9357	0.8073

3.3. Catalyst performance in the PBR and PBMR

The influence of reaction temperature and NH_3 weight hourly space velocity ($\text{WHSV}_{\text{NH}_3}$) on NH_3 conversion was assessed for both the packed bed reactor (PBR) and the packed bed membrane reactor (PBMR). The results were compared to results expected for equilibrium (Figure 6), calculated by using the correlations in refs. [10,15,66]. Specifically, in the PBMR, the impact of the Ar sweep gas ($\dot{V}_S = 554 \text{ NmL}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) was evaluated at 350°C with a $\text{WHSV}_{\text{NH}_3}$ of $1680 \text{ NmL}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$.

For both PBR and PBMR configurations, it was observed that NH_3 conversion increases exponentially with the temperature between 350 and 400°C and decreases as the $\text{WHSV}_{\text{NH}_3}$ decreases (Figure 6a – b).

The exponential dependence of the NH_3 conversion on the temperature is larger in the PBMR than the PBR, with the only exception of the PBR at $0.560 \text{ L}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ where a slight negative value is observed. The highest NH_3 conversions are achieved at $0.560 \text{ L}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ and 400°C and the lowest one at $1.680 \text{ L}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ and 350°C .

In all instances, NH_3 conversion was higher in PBMR using the sweep gas. Accordingly, operating with $\text{WHSV}_{\text{NH}_3}$ of $0.560 \text{ L}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ at 350°C , the NH_3 conversion increases from 21% in the PBR to 40% in the PBMR. Moreover, employing the same $\text{WHSV}_{\text{NH}_3}$ at 400°C , the PBMR configuration reaches an almost complete conversion (99%), slightly overcoming the equilibrium (98%). Using the PBR at the same $\text{WHSV}_{\text{NH}_3}$, the NH_3 conversion (97%) approaches the equilibrium (99%) only at 550°C (Figure 6b). Notably, in the absence of a sweep gas, the NH_3 conversion measured at 350°C and $1.680 \text{ L}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, is intermediate (17%) between the PBR configuration (13%) and that of the PBMR with sweep gas (24%).

Similarly to NH_3 conversion, the achieved hydrogen recovery factor (HRF) in PBMR increases exponentially with the temperature and increases with decreasing the $\text{WHSV}_{\text{NH}_3}$, reaching 94.9 % at $0.560 \text{ L}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ and 400°C (Figure 6c). At the same $\text{WHSV}_{\text{NH}_3}$, the HRF decreases to 61.4 and 30.5 % at 400° and 375°C , respectively. As compared with the previous results in the absence of Ar as a sweep gas, at 350°C and a $\text{WHSV}_{\text{NH}_3}$ of $1.680 \text{ NmL}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, the HRF is quite low (3.8%).

Figure 6. NH_3 conversion in the (a) PBMR (dashed lines and circular shapes) and PBR (dashed lines, triangular shapes) measured at 11 bar(a) and 350 , 375 , and 400°C employing different $\text{WHSV}_{\text{NH}_3}$ (definition in eq. SI.2); (b) NH_3 conversion in the PBR within the whole investigated temperature range; (c) hydrogen recovery factor; (d) productivity of purified hydrogen and membrane permeance (the continuous black line in (a) and (b) represent the equilibrium conversion; in the PBMR, $554 \text{ NmL}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ of Ar was fed as a sweep gas in countercurrent flow; the red square point at 350°C in (a) represents the conversion achieved using the PBMR in the absence of a sweep gas; experimental conditions: catalyst reduced at 350°C in H_2 for 3 h and tested with 10% NH_3 -Ar).

The productivity of purified hydrogen (PP_{H_2} , see eq. S9 in SI) increases exponentially as the temperature rises, as HRF (Figure 6d). However, except for a single value, at $0.560 \text{ L}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ and 400°C , all the curves at different $\text{WHSV}_{\text{NH}_3}$ overlap on each other, increasing from $16.5 \pm 0.5 \text{ mmol}_{\text{H}_2}\cdot\text{g}_{\text{Ru}}\cdot\text{min}$ at 350°C , to $53.5 \pm 0.5 \text{ mmol}_{\text{H}_2}\cdot\text{g}_{\text{Ru}}\cdot\text{min}$ at 400°C . Notably, in the absence of a sweep gas,

at $1.680 \text{ L} \cdot \text{g}^{-1} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$ and $350 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, PP_{H_2} is $5.4 \text{ mmol}_{\text{H}_2} \cdot \text{g}_{\text{Ru}}^{-1} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$, about 3 times lower than in the presence of the sweep gas. Moreover, as highlighted in the same figure, the latter parameter strongly correlates with the membrane permeance.

The exponential dependence of the NH_3 conversion on the temperature observed in the PBMR, compared to the PBR, is related to the synergistic dependence of the membrane's hydrogen permeance ($Q(T)/\delta$) and reaction kinetics [39,41]. The latter is less evident at $0.560 \text{ L} \cdot \text{g}^{-1} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$, as the conversion is approaching the equilibrium due to the increased importance of the reverse reaction. The observed conversion trends agree with the exponential increase of the HRF and PP_{H_2} with the temperature and in the presence of a sweep gas at a fixed volumetric flow. The importance of maintaining a driving force for H_2 separation is highlighted by the comparably low HRF and PP_{H_2} in the absence of a sweep gas, in agreement with previous results [34].

On the other side, the overlapping PP_{H_2} curves, considering the different NH_3 conversions obtained at the tested temperatures and $\text{WHSV}_{\text{NH}_3}$, indicate that the driving force over the longitudinal direction of the membrane for H_2 permeation at each temperature is similar for all the tested $\text{WHSV}_{\text{NH}_3}$. Therefore, at a constant sweep gas flow and high $\text{WHSV}_{\text{NH}_3}$, the NH_3 conversion is limited by the catalyst's kinetics equilibrating with the hydrogen permeation rates across the membrane. The observed HRF trends are in line with the latter hypothesis. Accordingly, it is expected that increasing the sweep gas flow or using a vacuum pump can increase the observed PP_{H_2} at $\text{WHSV}_{\text{NH}_3}$ larger or equals than $1.3 \text{ L} \cdot \text{g}^{-1} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$, further improving the NH_3 conversion. Therefore, in the reported conditions, the reaction is not limited by the permeance of the prepared membrane but by the high H_2 partial pressure in the permeate side of the membrane. On the other side, the slightly lower PP_{H_2} observed at $0.560 \text{ L} \cdot \text{g}^{-1} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$ and $400 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, when the NH_3 conversion is almost complete, compared to its corresponding value observed at 1.300 and $1.680 \text{ L} \cdot \text{g}^{-1} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$, was related to the low $\text{WHSV}_{\text{NH}_3}$. Therefore, considering the almost complete NH_3 conversion, HRF, and the high PP_{H_2} the performance achieved at $400 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $0.560 \text{ L} \cdot \text{g}^{-1} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$ can be considered as an optimum with respect to the $\text{WHSV}_{\text{NH}_3}$, reaction temperature, pressure, sweep gas flow and catalyst loading, minimising the use of Ru and Pd.

By comparing the performance achieved at the optimum point with the existing literature (see Table S3) at the same level of conversion, we obtained PP_{H_2} and HRF far larger than PBMRs coupled with a 20 wt. % BaCoCe using vacuum [35], 2 wt. % Ru/AC using Ar a sweep gas [34], and 0.5 wt. % Ru/ γ - Al_2O_3 [33]. Specifically, compared with the latter, we achieved a far better utilisation of Ru and Pd, which can be attributed mostly to the lower thickness of the Pd membrane reported here. Superior HRF (94.9 vs 66%), similar PP_{H_2} ($56.49 \text{ mmol}_{\text{H}_2} \cdot \text{g}_{\text{Ru}}^{-1} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$) and NH_3 conversion (98 - 99%) was obtained as compared with the Ru-based PBMR ref. in [38], probably due to the use of a sweep gas in our case. Much lower PP_{H_2} , and larger HRF (94.88% vs. 85 - 87 %) were obtained as compared with refs. [39] and [36], reporting a Ru-based CMR and a La-promoted Ru catalysts and PBMRs, respectively. Finally, comparable PP_{H_2} ($47 - 60 \text{ mmol}_{\text{H}_2} \cdot \text{g}_{\text{Ru}}^{-1} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$) HRF (94.88 - 98%) and an NH_3 conversion (99 - 100%) were achieved as compared with the Ru-based PBMR and the PBMR-CMR reported in ref. [33] and [31,32].

4. Conclusions

The obtained results show a clear enhancement in NH_3 conversion rates when utilising the PBMR configuration compared to the PBR specifically, at a WHSV of $0.560 \text{ L} \cdot \text{g}^{-1} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$ and a temperature of $400 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, NH_3 conversion in the PBMR nearly reached almost complete conversion (99%), surpassing the equilibrium conversion (98%) and significantly outperforming the PBR, which only approached the equilibrium conversion (97%) at $550 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, reaching purified hydrogen productivity

of $47 \text{ mmol}_{\text{H}_2} \cdot \text{g}_{\text{Ru}}^{-1} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$ and hydrogen recovery factors of 94.9 %. This result highlights the PBMR's capability to enhance hydrogen recovery effectively, especially compared to lower HRFs observed at different conditions, emphasising the reactor's efficiency in hydrogen separation and recovery. These improvements underscore the effectiveness of the PBMR, particularly when utilising sweep gas, which elevates NH_3 conversion by creating favourable transmembrane pressure gradients that facilitate hydrogen transfer. The same conclusions can be extended to other systems and reactions employing PBMR and sweep gases. Although using Ar, a sweep gas, is unsuitable practically, the obtained results can be extended to industrial uses using vacuum systems, a different sweep gas such as H_2O or by coupling hydrogen-consuming reactions to produce valuable chemicals within the permeate side of the membrane.

Using diluted ammonia mixtures, a rational combination of a 1.3 wt. % Ru eggshell catalyst and an ultra-thin Pd membrane demonstrated comparable or even superior performance in terms of hydrogen productivity, recovery factor, and ammonia conversion compared to similar systems reported in the literature. This approach not only maximises hydrogen permeance and productivity but also enhances the efficiency of noble metal utilisation at a fixed sweep ratio. Employing a diluted (10%) NH_3 feed reduces the risks associated with handling and storing concentrated ammonia, supports effective use of minimal noble metals, ensures safer operations, and aligns with environmental standards. The diluent can then be recirculated. Thus, this approach can be proposed as a valuable technology for using NH_3 as a hydrogen carrier.

Finally, these results indicate good perspectives of this technology for recovering H_2 from waste-diluted ammonia streams. Further studies are being conducted to evaluate the sensitivity of the catalyst and membrane to possible poisoning elements present in the waste ammonia stream and the effect of N_2 . However, the preliminary indications suggest the suitability of this technology, which allows the valorisation of ammonia waste to produce H_2 .

In summary, these results demonstrate promising performance for integrated PBMRs using diluted ammonia and optimised noble metal catalysts to enhance NH_3 decomposition, H_2 permeability, and hydrogen recovery. Future works should regard the multivariable optimisation of such systems (catalyst loading, promoters, location in the PBMR, membrane thickness, and surface/volume ratios) and their applicability for the valorisation of diluted ammonia streams by using real or simulated mixtures.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Conceptualisation, S.A., G.G., G.C; methodology, G.G., S.A.; validation, G.G., D.M.; formal analysis, D.M., C.I.; investigation, G.G.; resources, G.C. and S.P.; data curation, G.G., D.M., C.I; writing—original draft preparation, D.M.; writing—review and editing, G.G., S.A.; visualisation, S.A.; supervision, S.A., G.C., S.P.; project administration, S.A.; funding acquisition, G.C., S.P. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Supplementary Data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at

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